

BUILDING STUDENT ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION

I Nyoman Nurcaya¹, Ni Ketut Seminari²

^{1,2}Udayana University – Bali

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Abstract: Entrepreneurship is one way that can be used to solve unemployment problems in a country. The Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (FEB UNUD) has also done its best to adjust the curriculum and learning process to support entrepreneurial activities. However, raising an interest in entrepreneurship is not an easy job. This is evident from the low interest of students to try entrepreneurship. The purpose of writing this article is to find out how the impact of Entrepreneurial Motivation and Opportunity Recognition has on interest in entrepreneurship which is moderated by leadership commitment at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University. The research was conducted on 115 (one hundred and fifteen) students who had taken entrepreneurship education using the Moderate Regression Analysis (MRA) analysis technique with the PLS approach. The results of the study show that entrepreneurial motivation and opportunity recognition have a significant positive effect on the interest in entrepreneurship. Leadership commitment is able to strengthen the effect of entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial intentions, but is unable to significantly strengthen the influence of opportunity recognition on entrepreneurial intentions. The results of this study can be used as a policy basis for creating programs to increase intentions in entrepreneurship for students. Increased motivation and recognition of business opportunities encourage students to have entrepreneurial intentions especially supported by leadership commitment.

Keywords: Motivation; Opportunity Recognition; Commitment; Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is one way that can be used to solve unemployment problems in a country. The development of entrepreneurial intention in society will be able to create new businesses that can create jobs, so that unemployment and poverty will be reduced. Entrepreneurship is an important issue in the economy of a developing nation. High entrepreneurial growth will bring an extraordinary increase in economic growth for a country. A country that has high entrepreneurship will encourage an increase in its economy. The ability to seize business opportunities and entrepreneurship education are important factors that link one's personal traits with entrepreneurial intentions (Kumar et al., 2019)

As a higher education institution, Udayana University is expected to be able to produce graduates who have good intellectual abilities and skills. In managing education, Unud follows the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards. In the regulation it is stated that one form of learning container is entrepreneurship (Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards, 2020). The support of university leaders is needed in increasing student interest in entrepreneurship (Omer & Aljaaidi, 2020).

The decision to become an entrepreneur is a process that takes a long time to form. In the existing literature, intention is often seen as a prerequisite for actual behavior. Intention is the first step in a series of potential entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, entrepreneurial intention is considered as the simplest and most effective predictor of behavior (Haque Choudhury & Mandal, 2021). Existing research mostly draws on cognitive models for Entrepreneurial Intention to explain entrepreneurial decisions. Among these models, the most prominent is the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) put forward by Ajzen (Haque Choudhury & Mandal, 2021). The intention to do entrepreneurship for students in the Faculty of Economics

and Business, Udayana University (FEB Unud), especially in the Undergraduate Study Program is still relatively low. Based on a report from the Entrepreneurship Development Unit at Udayana University in 2019, only 12 students from FEB Unud were registered. This number is very low compared to the number of active undergraduate study program students of 3020 (Yowani, 2019).

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Theory of Planned Behavior

Theory of Planned Behavior is a theory that focuses on studying interest. This theory was developed in 1991 by Ajzen who studied intention as a tool for predicting one's behavior (Nguyen et al., 2022). Several studies have tried to apply the Theory of Planned Behavior to predict the intention to choose a job status. The employment status referred to here is working as a salaried employee, or self-employed (self-employed). The entrepreneurial intention of entrepreneurs by using Theory of Planned Behavior is associated with the experience of being an entrepreneur who has experienced failure in the past. Most of the Theory of Planned Behavior studies focus on the study of entrepreneurial intentions (Kautonen et al., 2015).

In the context of entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial intentions can be used to predict entrepreneurial behavior in the future. The results of the study prove that Entrepreneurship Education and Business Motivation provide a strong stimulus for students to develop an Interest in Entrepreneurship (Bharatha, 2019). Entrepreneurial intention is someone's intention to choose a career as an independent entrepreneur. Entrepreneurial interest reflects one's commitment to starting a new business and is a central issue that needs attention in understanding the entrepreneurial process of starting a new business.

Entrepreneurial intention can also be interpreted as the first step in the process of establishing a business which is generally long-term in nature. The results of the study prove that student entrepreneurship self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions and career adaptation, and career adaptability has a significant and positive effect on entrepreneurship intentions. Career adaptation is able to mediate the effect of entrepreneurial self-efficacy on entrepreneurship intentions partially (Qiao & Huang, 2019). Interest in entrepreneurship is a determination to do entrepreneurship with specific goals that are owned by individuals. Entrepreneurial interest is a representation of planned actions to do entrepreneurship. The results of the study show that cultural variables (and material variables) have a significant influence on entrepreneurial intentions, while social variables do not have a significant impact on entrepreneurial intentions (Kholid Mawardi, 2020).

The ability to come up with ideas is an important factor in an entrepreneurship. The idea in entrepreneurship is a complete set of ideas that a person has, which consists of a person's mentality which can be accessed occasionally for commercialization (Bharatha, 2019). An idea doesn't have to be transformed or shaped into an opportunity. An idea will remain an idea as long as nothing is done to develop the idea and no effort is made to minimize uncertainty. Therefore, an idea is not an opportunity in entrepreneurship, but no opportunity will arise without the creation of an idea.

Motivation has been found to be a key construct in entrepreneurship research. Entrepreneurial motivation was originally developed in the domestic environment to explain the behavior of the drivers of the entrepreneurial process. The results of the article review show that motivation has been found as a key construct in international entrepreneurship (IE) research, which has two characteristics of motivation, namely entrepreneurship and its implementation (Dimitratos et al., 2016). Entrepreneurial interest can be increased by understanding the motivation of human behavior is the result of a process of motivational and cognitive factors (abilities, knowledge and skills). This motivation has a direct effect on entrepreneurial intentions

Opportunity recognition is the process by which ideas for business ventures that may be profitable are identified by an individual (Hassan et al., 2020). Opportunity recognition is defined as an individual's ability to recognize, discover or construct patterns and concepts (Bianchi, 2017). Today many sources of information assist entrepreneurs in identifying opportunities. Advances in information technology make access to appropriate information very easy (Ghezali & Boudi, 2020). However, computer literacy and internet literacy do not always have a significant impact on entrepreneurial behavior (Islami, 2019)

From based on previous theory and research, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1 : Entrepreneurial motivation has a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention

H2 : The opportunities recognition has a positive effect on entrepreneurship intention

H3 : Leadership commitment can strengthen influence entrepreneurial motivation towards entrepreneurial intention

H4 : Leadership commitment can strengthen influence opportunities recognition toward entrepreneurial intention

Figure 1: Research Model Building Student Entrepreneurial Intention

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research belongs to the type of associative research, which is research that aims to determine the effect/relationship between two variables or even more. The location of this research is the Faculty of Economics and Business, Udayana University (Bali). The number of samples used were 115 students who had taken the Entrepreneurship course. Data analyzed with Moderation Analysis (Moderate Regression Analysis / MRA) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach.

The variables used in this study can be identified as follows:

Entrepreneurial Intention (Y). There are five indicators used to measure interest in entrepreneurship (Kumar & Das, 2019). Students intend to develop an independent business (y1); Students intend to form an entrepreneurial team (y2); Students intend to write a new business plan (y3); Students intend to find a place for entrepreneurship (y4); and Students enjoy participating in entrepreneurial competitions (y5)

Entrepreneurial Motivation (X1). There are four indicators used to measure the variable Entrepreneurial Motivation (Kumar & Das, 2019). Entrepreneurship gives a sense of pride (x1.1); Can give work to others (x1.2); Entrepreneurship makes students an independent person (x1.3); Entrepreneurship gives students better business skills (x1.4)

Opportunity recognition (X2). Opportunity recognition is a student's ability to find and get profitable creative business ideas (Hassan et al., 2020). The measurement of opportunity recognition uses four indicators, namely students find many business opportunities (x2.1); Students easily find business opportunities (x2.2); There are many new product innovation opportunities that can be developed by students (x2.3); Students find many business opportunities on the internet (x2.4)

Leadership Commitment (M). The measurement of leadership commitment uses four indicators (Shi et al., 2019). The curriculum offers courses on entrepreneurship (m1); There is a policy to hold workshops on entrepreneurship (m2); There is a policy of offering competition that focuses on entrepreneurship (m3); Policy in place to offer internships/practical work focused on entrepreneurship (m4)

4. RESULTS

Instrument Validity Test

Questionnaires used in research must meet the requirements of the validity test, namely the test used to measure the ability of an instrument to measure what it should measure. A research instrument is declared valid if it has a correlation coefficient between statement items and a total score in the instrument greater than 0.300 with an Alpha error rate of 0.05. The results of the analysis show that all correlation coefficients between items with a total score are above 0.300.

Reliability Test. The reliability test of the research instrument uses the Alpha Cronbach value. The purpose of the reliability test is to measure the level of reliability of the instrument to measure data when it is used repeatedly. Cronbach's Alpha value is declared reliable if the value is greater than or equal to 0.60 (Hair Jr et al., 2017). The results of the analysis show that all variables have a Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.6.

Assessment of the outer model or measurement model

Measurement model is a way to measure the validity of the model. This test is carried out before discussing hypothesis testing. PLS has two criteria for assessing the outer model, namely convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity is assessed based on average variance extracted (AVE) and composite reliability (Hair Jr et al., 2017). Data analysis techniques with the Smart PLS application, the outer model assessment is carried out by looking at convergent validity (the magnitude of the loading factor for each construct). This study uses a minimum loading factor limit of 0.5.

Table 1: Outer Loadings

	M	Y	X1*M	X1	X2*M	X2
X1*M			1.019			
X2*M					1010	
m1	0.865					
m2	0.822					
m3	0893					
m4	0.846					
x1.1				0.888		
x1.2				0.853		
x1.3				0896		
x1.4				0.740		
x2.1						0.885
x2.2						0.830
x2.3						0893
x2.4						0.803
y1		0.819				
y2		0.851				
y3		0.819				
y4		0.820				
y5		0.861				

The results in Table 1 show that the outer model values meet the convergent validity criteria where each indicator has a factor loading value above 0.50. It can be concluded that the construct has good convergent validity.

Discriminant validity

A research model must meet the discriminant validity test (Discriminant validity). Discriminant validity is measured based on the cross loading value. If the cross loading indicator value has the greatest value in the construct it reflects, then the indicator is declared valid as a reflection of the construct.

Table 2: Cross Loading

	M	Y	X1*M	X1	X2*M	X2
X1*M	0.040	0.221	1,000	0.099	0.358	-0.018
X2*M	0.053	0.091	0.358	-0.019	1,000	0.012
m1	0.865	0.447	0.075	0.311	0.089	0.266
m2	0.822	0.257	-0.031	0.148	0.042	0.371
m3	0893	0.417	0.045	0.345	0.015	0.349
m4	0.846	0.359	0.016	0.221	0.029	0.351
x1.1	0.282	0.481	0.061	0.888	-0.033	0.390
x1.2	0.261	0.424	0.148	0.853	0.000	0.343
x1.3	0.290	0.503	0.092	0896	0.015	0.381

x1.4	0.227	0.447	0.037	0.740	-0.046	0.235
x2.1	0.321	0.436	-0.048	0.319	-0.036	0.885
x2.2	0.359	0.422	-0.015	0.403	-0.012	0.830
x2.3	0.317	0.449	-0.039	0.353	0.067	0.893
x2.4	0.306	0.342	0.054	0.286	0.021	0.803
y1	0.297	0.819	0.228	0.496	0.104	0.323
y2	0.404	0.851	0.169	0.481	0.082	0.471
y3	0.349	0.819	0.233	0.505	0.089	0.351
y4	0.374	0.820	0.122	0.413	0.027	0.456
y5	0.431	0.861	0.173	0.401	0.079	0.418

The results of the analysis as shown in Table 2 show that the cross loading value for each indicator is the highest in the construct it represents. The cross loading value is already smaller, there are other constructs.

Model reliability test

The reliability or reliability of a construct can be assessed from composite reliability. The composite reliability value serves to measure internal consistency and the value must be above 0.60. A different way that can be used is to compare the AVE roots with the correlation between constructs. The AVE value must be above 0.5 and the correlation between constructs must be lower than the smallest AVE root(Ghozali, 2008).

Table 3: Composite Reliability

Variable	Composite Reliability
Commitment Leadership	0.917
Interest_Entrepreneurship	0.920
Motivation*Commitment	1,000
Motivation_Entrepreneurship	0.910
Opportunity*Commitment	1,000
Introduction_Opportunity	0.915

The results of the analysis in Table 3 show that the composite reliability value of all constructs is above 0.60. This shows that the model is reliable. Another way to test the reliability of the model is by comparing the root value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between the construct and the other constructs.

Table 4: AVE and Root of AVE

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Root AVE
Commitment_Leadership	0.734	0.857
Interest_Entrepreneurship	0.696	0.834
Motiv*Commitment	1,000	1,000
Motivation_Entrepreneurship	0.717	0.847
Opportunity*Commitment	1,000	1,000
Introduction_Opportunity	0.728	0.853

The AVE Root values in Table 4 will be compared with the correlation values between latent variables as shown in Table 5

Table 5: Correlation between Latent Variables

	M	Y	X1*M	X1	X2*M	X2
M	1,000	0.446	0.040	0.314	0.053	0.381
Y	0.446	1,000	0.221	0.550	0.091	0.486
X1*M	0.040	0.221	1,000	0.099	0.358	-0.018
X1	0.314	0.550	0.099	1,000	-0.019	0.401
X2*M	0.053	0.091	0.358	-0.019	1,000	0.012
X2	0.381	0.486	-0.018	0.401	0.012	1,000

Table 5 shows that the correlation value of this construct with other constructs is already less than 0.834 (the smallest AVE root in Table 4). This shows that the model is reliable.

Structural model testing (inner model)

Testing the structural model (Inner model) describes the relationship between latent variables based on substantive theory. In assessing the model with PLS, it starts by looking at the R-squares for each endogenous variable. The results of testing the inner model using the R-square value are presented in Table 6

Table 6: Value R Square

Endogenous Variables	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Interest_Entrepreneurship	0.465	0.440

Based on the results of the analysis in Table 6, it can be seen that the R-square value of the Interest in Entrepreneurship variable is 0.465. The R square value shows that 46.50% Interest in Entrepreneurship can be explained by the variables Entrepreneurial Motivation, Opportunity Recognition, Leadership Commitment, Interaction of Entrepreneurial Motivation with Leadership Commitment and Opportunity Recognition interactions with Leadership Commitment. 53.50% Interest in Entrepreneurship is determined by variables outside the model.

Figure 2: Diagram of the Leadership Commitment Role Model Moderating the Effect of Entrepreneurial Motivation and Opportunity Recognition on Interest in Entrepreneurship

The structural model in Figure 2 is referred to as a reflexive model. This model hypothesizes that changes in latent constructs will affect changes in indicators.

5). Hypothesis test

Testing the hypothesis about the effect of Entrepreneurial Motivation and Opportunity Recognition on Entrepreneurial Interest moderated by Leadership Commitment is present in Table 7

Table 7: Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Means (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
M -> Y	0.227	0.227	0.086	2,643	0.008
X1*M -> Y	0.171	0.157	0.082	2076	0.038
X1 -> Y	0.358	0.363	0.084	4,285	0.000
X2*M -> Y	0.020	0.017	0.081	0.250	0.802
X2 -> M	0.259	0.263	0.092	2,822	0.005

Table 7 shows the results of testing the hypothesis for each relationship between constructs. The original sample value is the estimated value of the relationship while the p value is the significance value of the existing relationship. The PLS application performs hypothesis testing with the bootstrapping method on the sample. The bootstrapping method is used to minimize data abnormality problems. This study uses an Alpha value of 5%. Table 7 shows that there are four (4) significant positive relationships with a p-value below 0.05 and one relationship (Opportunity recognition*Leadership Commitment) is not significant with a p-value.

5. DISCUSSION

Build interest in entrepreneurship among students very important to reduce the number of unemployed in Indonesia. Entrepreneurs can increase economic growth. Building an entrepreneurial spirit has become a demand in the world of education in many countries. Entrepreneurship curriculum as an academic policy in tertiary institutions is expected to encourage students to have an entrepreneurial spirit. Entrepreneurial skills will be able to improve the performance of new businesses, expand employment so that graduates become quality graduates (Cui & Bell, 2022; Iwu et al., 2021).

Leadership support in developing educational institutions capable of creating an entrepreneurial spirit is needed. Changing the mindset of students about looking for work by creating jobs can be done through changes to the curriculum (Handayati et al., 2020). This can be done by bringing up entrepreneurship courses or inserting entrepreneurship topics into certain courses. The support provided by the leaders of higher education institutions to encourage the birth of entrepreneurs can also be carried out through entrepreneurial competitions, conducting workshops, and internships that can stimulate students to become entrepreneurs. (Kumar et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurial motivation as a stimulus from within the student to entrepreneurship needs attention. This stimulation can be generated by explaining some of the benefits that can be obtained by entrepreneurship, such as being proud to give jobs to other people, being proud to be independent and having the authority to control the business. How many studies support the findings of this study which state that there is a significant effect of entrepreneurial motivation on entrepreneurial interest (Bharata, 2019). Entrepreneurial motivation that exists in students will have a stronger impact on the interest in entrepreneurship if it is supported by leadership commitment. Policies to encourage interest in entrepreneurship need to be improved.

Interest in entrepreneurship can also grow because students see business opportunities. The introduction of opportunities will be able to make students the types of businesses that exist and the benefits they will get. The development of information technology makes it easy for students to see existing business opportunities. The pattern of public consumption behavior will be easy to observe on existing website media and social media. Based on the existing opportunities, students will be able to choose the type of business that they are able to apply and provide higher benefits (Zainol & Al Mamun, 2018).

The introduction of opportunities regarding entrepreneurship has been shown to significantly influence the interest in entrepreneurship. However, leadership commitment is not proven to be able to strengthen the influence of opportunity recognition on entrepreneurial interest. Although entrepreneurship opportunities are easy to find, they are not in accordance with the support provided by the leadership. The curriculum, which is a form of leadership support, needs to include studies on the role of technology in entrepreneurship. Provision of adequate information technology infrastructure also needs attention.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that has been carried out, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- a) Entrepreneurial motivation has a significant positive effect on entrepreneurial intention. These results indicate that the higher the motivation for entrepreneurship, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship from students.
- b) The opportunities recognition has a significant positive effect on the interest in entrepreneurship. These results indicate that the more often students are introduced to business opportunities, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship from students
- c) Leadership commitment is able to strengthen the influence of entrepreneurial motivation on student entrepreneurship intention.
- d) Leadership commitment is not able to strengthen the influence of opportunity recognition on entrepreneurial intention.

Further Study

This research has limitations in terms of research area. This study only took samples from one faculty. Researchers can then develop this research to be broader, for example in one university or all universities in one province or country.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Bharata, W. (2019). The Influence of Entrepreneurship Education and Business Motivation on Entrepreneurial Interests (Study on Students of the Faculty of Economics, University of Muhammadiyah Ponorogo). *Journal of Economics and Management*, 2(2), 98–113.
- [2] Bianchi, C. (2017). SME International Performance in Latin America The Role of entrepreneurial and Technological Capabilities. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24(1), 176–195. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-09-2016-0142>
- [3] Cui, J., & Bell, R. (2022). Behavioural entrepreneurial mindset: How entrepreneurial education activity impacts entrepreneurial intention and behaviour. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(2), 100639. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2022.100639>
- [4] Dimitratos, P., Buck, T., Fletcher, M., & Li, N. (2016). The motivation of international entrepreneurship: The case of Chinese transnational entrepreneurs. *International Business Review*, 25(5), 1103–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2016.01.012>
- [5] Ghezali, F., & Boudi, A. (2020). The moderating effect of information technology capabilities on the relationship between marketing mix and corporate entrepreneurship. *PSU Research Review*, ahead-of-p(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/prr-12-2019-0037>
- [6] Ghozali, I. (2008). *Structural Equation Modeling: Metode Alternatif Dengan Partial Least Square*. BP. Universitas Diponegoro.
- [7] Hair Jr, J. F., M.Hult, G. T., M. RIngle, C., & Sartstedt, M. (2017). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM)* (Second). Sage.
- [8] Handayati, P., Wulandari, D., Soetjipto, B. E., Wibowo, A., & Narmaditya, B. S. (2020). Does entrepreneurship education promote vocational students' entrepreneurial mindset? *Heliyon*, 6(11), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05426>
- [9] Haque Choudhury, A., & Mandal, S. (2021). The role of familial, social, educational and business environmental factors on entrepreneurial intention among university students in Bangladesh. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, xxxx, 3–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.03.256>
- [10] Hassan, A., Saleem, I., Anwar, I., & Hussain, S. A. (2020). Entrepreneurial intention of Indian university students: the role of opportunity recognition and entrepreneurship education. *Education and Training*, 62(7–8), 843–861. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ET-02-2020-0033>
- [11] Islami, N. N. (2019). The effect of digital literacy toward entrepreneur behaviors through students' intention entrepreneurship on Economics Education Study Program at Jember. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 243(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/243/1/012084>
- [12] Iwu, C. G., Opute, P. A., Nchu, R., Eresia-Eke, C., Tengeh, R. K., Jaiyeoba, O., & Aliyu, O. A. (2021). Entrepreneurship education, curriculum and lecturer-competency as antecedents of student entrepreneurial intention. *International Journal of Management Education*, 19(1), 0–1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2019.03.007>
- [13] Kautonen, T., van Gelderen, M., & Fink, M. (2015). Robustness of the theory of planned behavior in predicting entrepreneurial intentions and actions. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 39(3), 655–674. <https://doi.org/10.1111/etap.12056>

- [14] Kholid Mawardi, M. (2020). Ecosytem Kewirausahaan Dan Dampaknya Pada Minat Berwirausaha. *Profit*, 14(02), 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.profit.2020.014.02.5>
- [15] Kumar, S., & Das, S. (2019). An extended model of theory of planned behaviour: Entrepreneurial intention, regional institutional infrastructure and perceived gender discrimination in India. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 11(3), 369–391. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-09-2018-0089>
- [16] Kumar, S., Das, S., Sivathanu, B., Pillai, R., Shi, L., Yao, X., Wu, W., Salisu, I., Hashim, N., Mashi, M. S., Aliyu, H. G., Vaitoonkiat, E., Charoensukmongkol, P., Erista, I. F. S., Andadari, R. K., Usmanij, P. A., Ratten, V., Cho, Y. H., Lee, J.-H., ... Oflazoglu, S. (2019). Perseverance of effort and consistency of interest for entrepreneurial career success: Does resilience matter? *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 12(2), 369–391. <https://doi.org/10.1108/apjie-05-2018-0028>
- [17] Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia No. 3 Tahun 2020 tentang Standar Nasional Pendidikan Tinggi, (2020).
- [18] Nguyen, D. T., Tran, V. D., & Ghafoor, A. (2022). The Impact of Covid-19 lockdown on Intention to Follow Preventive Measures in Vietnam: Integrated Protection Motivation Theory and Theory Planed Behavior. *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2054502>
- [19] Omer, W., & Aljaaidi, K. (2020). The association of entrepreneurial education and support with Entrepreneurial intention at northern boarder university: the case of students from college of business administration. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 8(1), 555–572. [https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1\(39\)](https://doi.org/http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.1(39))
- [20] Qiao, X., & Huang, J.-H. (2019). Effect of College Students' Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy on Entrepreneurial Intention: Career Adaptability as a Mediating Variable. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 5(3), 305–313. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ijem.5.3.305>
- [21] Shi, L., Yao, X., & Wu, W. (2019). Perceived university support, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, heterogeneous entrepreneurial intentions in entrepreneurship education: The moderating role of the Chinese sense of face. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 12(2), 205–230. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-04-2019-0040>
- [22] Yowani, C. (2019). *Unit Pengembangan Kewirausahaan Universitas Udayana*.
- [23] Zainol, N. R., & Al Mamun, A. (2018). Entrepreneurial competency, competitive advantage and performance of informal women micro-entrepreneurs in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*, 12(3), 299–321. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-11-2017-0090>